

CARE guidelines for case reports: 13-item checklist

Please indicate in which section each item has been reported in your manuscript. If you feel that an item does not apply to your manuscript, please enter N/A.

For more information about the CARE guidelines, please see <http://www.care-statement.org/>.

No.	Description	Section #
Title		
1	The area of focus and “case report” should appear in the title	page 1, line 1
Keywords		
2	Two to five key words that identify topics covered in this case report	page 1, line 33-34
Abstract		
3a	Introduction—What is unique about this case? What does it add to the medical literature?	page 1, line 17-20
3b	The main symptoms of the patient and the important clinical findings	page 1, line 21-23
3c	The main diagnoses, therapeutics interventions, and outcomes	Page 1, line 21, 24-26
3d	Conclusion—What are the main ‘take-away’ lessons from this case?	Page 1, line 29-31
Introduction		
4	Briefly summarize why this case is unique with medical literature references	Page 2, line 41-45
Patient information		
5a	De-identified demographic information and other patient specific information	Page 2, line 55
5b	Main concerns and symptoms of the patient	Page 2, line 56-60
5c	Medical, family, and psychosocial history including relevant genetic information	Page 2, line 60-61
5d	Relevant past interventions and their outcomes	Page 2, line 61
Clinical findings		
6	Describe the relevant physical examination (PE) and other clinical findings	Page 2, line 62-66
Timeline		
7	A timeline of relevant information from the patient’s history and this episode of care	Page 2, line 57-58
Diagnostics assessment		
8a	Diagnostic methods (such as PE, laboratory testing, imaging, surveys)	Page 2, line 67-68 Page 3, line 69-82
8b	Diagnostic challenges (such as access, financial, or cultural)	Page 3, line 73-75; line

		85-86
8c	Diagnostic reasoning including a differential diagnosis	Page 3, line 92-93
8d	Prognostic characteristics (such as staging in oncology) where applicable	
Therapeutic intervention		
9a	Types of intervention (such as pharmacologic, surgical, preventive, self-care)	Page 3, line 83- 87; 94-97
9b	Administration of intervention (such as dosage, strength, duration)	Page 3, line 94-97
9c	Changes in intervention with rationale	Page 3, line 101- 102 Page 4, line 103- 107
Follow-up and outcomes		
10a	Clinician and patient-assessed outcomes when appropriate	Page 3, line 86-87
10b	Important follow-up diagnostic and other test results	Page 3, line 101- 102
10c	Intervention adherence and tolerability (how was this assessed?)	Page 4, line 108- 110
10d	Adverse and unanticipated events	
Discussion		
11a	Discussion of the strengths and limitations in your approach to this case	Page 6, Line 183- 186
11b	Discussion of the relevant medical literature	Page 4-6, Line 115- 197
11c	The rationale for conclusions (including assessment of possible causes)	Page 6-7, Line 200- 206
11d	The primary “take-away” lessons of this case report	Page 6-7, Line 200- 206
Patient perspective		
12	When appropriate, the patient can share their perspective on their case	
Informed consent		
13	The patient should give informed consent	Page 7, Line 211- 212

When submitting your manuscript via the online submission form, please upload the completed checklist as a Figure/supplementary file.

If you would like this checklist to be included alongside your article, we ask that you upload the completed checklist to an online repository and include the guideline type, name of the repository, DOI and license in the *Data availability* section of your manuscript.

H, Werthmann PG, Moher D, Rison RA, Shamseer L, Koch CA, Sun GH, Hanaway P, Sudak NL, Kaszkin-Bettag M, Carpenter JE, Gagnier JJ. CARE guidelines for case reports: explanation and elaboration document. *J Clin Epidemiol.* 2017 May 18. pii: S0895-4356(17)30037-9. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclinepi.2017.04.026>